

Auditing Machine Behaviors: Does a diverse crowd result in different social norms?

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Abstract—Many intelligent systems depend on black-box services for achieving goals. For example, Decision Support Systems (DSS) incorporate image tagging services for translating the content of an image into useful information that serves the purpose of the system under development (e.g., facilitating hiring decisions). Auditing the results of DSS for fairness can thus become a cumbersome process as they are correlated with the output of the black-box image tagger. In this work, we assume that tags generated by an image tagger are part of the DSS and in terms of fairness can be considered socially acceptable or unacceptable conforming to the varying goals of a DSS. For example, the tag “good-looking” can be considered appropriate in a dating context but inappropriate in a hiring context. We propose a methodology for leveraging the use of crowdsourcing as an approach for auditing what is socially acceptable and unacceptable for tags generated by black-box image taggers. As a first step, we attempt to understand how the crowdworkers perceive (un)acceptable tags in two scenarios: (i) a hiring DSS, and (ii) a dating DSS. Through our analysis, we investigate how answers (in our case tags) received by crowdworkers representing different demographic groups (i.e., country of residence and gender) impact the auditing process. Results indicate that varying the DSS scenario, and the demographics of the crowdworkers, yields a different fairness perspective concurrent to the “acceptable” and “unacceptable” social norms.

Index Terms—AI auditing, crowdsourcing, diversity, images

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has undergone a process of “democratization” during the past several years, putting AI tools, techniques and components into the hands of more people, experts and non-experts alike [1]. Cognitive Computing refers to the large-scale deployment of AI technologies via the Cloud [2], and is a key process through which AI is being democratized. Many industry giants now offer a range of Cognitive Services, such as those supporting computer vision (e.g., Google Cloud Vision), search (e.g., Amazon CloudSearch, Google Search) or natural language processing (e.g.,

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Microsoft Azure speech-to-text). Third parties can access these services for a fee, typically via RESTful APIs. This allows almost any developer or researcher to incorporate state-of-the-art intelligent algorithms into their own developed decision-support systems (DSS). In fact, the Gartner 2022 Hype Cycle for AI describes AI Cloud Services as being over their “peak of inflated expectations,” reaching full maturity soon.¹

It is challenging to evaluate fairness and transparency of AI systems and processes, and the use of proprietary Cognitive Services further complicates this. Sometimes, it is inevitable that a system will result in discrimination against individuals and/or groups of people, especially when algorithms/services have been deployed as part of an AI system that judges people or artifacts (e.g., images, audio, texts) that depict or represent people. For example, image tagging services such as Clarifai [3], rely on computer vision algorithms that generate a set of descriptive tags (e.g., “man”, “asian”, “attractive”) in response to an input image of a person. Given the general nature of such services, a number of questions concerning their behaviors arises. Some of the most critical questions concern whether the behaviors of the algorithms align with human social norms. For instance, when analyzing an image of a person, should the algorithms mention *inferred characteristics*, such as the person’s race, or if they are “attractive” or “over-/underweight”? Would the answers to this question change if the tags were integrated into a DSS that screens resumes of job candidates? And will our views change again if they are used within a different application, such as auto-archiving in a personal photo collection? It is obvious that the “social behaviors”, or the way these machines interpret people, must be audited for different contexts and audiences.

Auditing techniques are commonly used as a means to evaluate group fairness in AI systems - whether or not a group of people (or artifacts) from protected classes experience a different treatment as compared to the majority, or to the whole population [4]. Auditing AI algorithms approaches have been classified into five group auditing design approaches [5] such as: a) code audits, b) noninvasive user audits, c) scraping au-

¹<https://www.gartner.com/en/articles/what-s-new-in-artificial-intelligence-from-the-2022-gartner-hype-cycle>

dits, d) sock puppet audits, and e) crowdsourced/collaborative audits. Bandy [6], noting that algorithm audits have become more common as more deployed systems display problematic behaviors, outlined four types of undesirable behaviors that can be uncovered by audits – discrimination, distortion of the facts/reality, exploitation and misjudgement of people.

In most of these studies, developers or researchers who have technical expertise take the role of the auditor, having as a consequence to propagate the auditor’s cultural blindspots during auditing [7]. Another issue is that some of these approaches (e.g., code audits) require that the auditor have full access to the system under study. On the other hand, in crowdsourced audits, independent users take the role of the auditor and this is an especially beneficial technique since it can harvest opinions from a large and diverse group, specifically when recruiting participants through crowdsourcing platforms, such as Amazon Mechanical Turk. Theoretically, crowdsourced auditing, has the potential to enrich an audit’s outcome with opinions influenced by different societal and educational backgrounds, thus reducing the statistical and personal bias of a single or just a few auditors. However, it is yet to be established how one may capture the benefit of crowdsourced auditing and how it compares with existing approaches.

A. Our Approach

We present a feasibility study for our crowdsourced audit method applied to the case of proprietary image analysis services. We envision the case in which a developer integrates a service such as Clarifai into his/her own DSS solution; thus, the behaviors of the external service may affect the quality – and the fairness – of the final decisions taken. Our approach explores the “acceptable” and “unacceptable” behaviors of image taggers given a DSS application scenario with the aid of crowdworkers. In this respect, our study is framed in terms of human social norms. We hypothesize that social norms, i.e., which tags are “acceptable” or “unacceptable” when describing people images, vary according to the scenario (hiring v. dating DSS). Furthermore, we hypothesize that crowdworkers with different demographic backgrounds will express different beliefs as to how the image tagging algorithm should behave. Thus, the following RQ is addressed: *Does a diverse crowd provide a different set of “acceptable” and “unacceptable” tags?* To explore this, we ask crowdworkers, both males and females, from two culturally different countries, Germany and Italy, to provide, in an open crowdsourcing task, appropriate and inappropriate output tags of an image tagging algorithm.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Crowdsourcing as an Approach for Auditing AI Systems

The use of crowdsourcing for auditing an AI system is mainly useful when real-world observations are important to evaluate the system [8]. In one type of crowdsourced audit, volunteers take the role of auditor. In Mozilla’s RegretsReporter browser extension users voluntarily add examples of their experience with harmful recommendations of YouTube’s algorithm [9]. Similarly, diverse users volunteer to produce

crowdsourced failure reports to describe in their own words, machine learning failures in different systems so that developers can detect AI errors [10]. In addition, in [11], the authors introduce systems for diverse users to lead their own audits of harmful algorithm behavior.

The most popular type of crowdsourced audit is the data collection from users who are recruited through a crowdsourcing platform to independently evaluate a system following a specific task. For instance, in [12] crowdworkers were asked to evaluate the Apple News system with regard to any social, political, and economic implications. In addition, Kay et al. [13] recruit workers on Amazon Mechanical Turk to detect any stereotypes in image search results for employment-related queries. A recent study [14] uses crowdsourcing to audit web search engines and they found that different crowdworkers tend to obtain different search results for the same queries, related to the country in which they are located. Crowdsourced audit has also been used in Mandel et al. [15], where the workers were asked to interact with a rule-based interface that generates AI system constraints and then to identify harmful behavior of AI systems. Contrary to these studies, our crowdsourcing methodology is an indirect way of auditing a DSS system that makes use of a proprietary image tagger. Crowdworkers are asked to provide their beliefs on the tags that can be harmful and those that they consider appropriate. As mentioned before, our work provides a feasibility study exploring the potentials of these indirect approaches in terms of exploring “acceptable” and “unacceptable” tags. We envision the collection of tags as a means to audit a DSS system, exposing what is considered socially acceptable and unacceptable by people with certain demographic characteristics.

B. Crowdsourced evaluations: A diverse group of evaluators

An important question for designing a crowdsourcing task for auditing an AI system is whether the involvement of a diverse crowd is important or not. Few works already study this assumption by conducting a crowdsourcing task where participants without any technical expertise had to audit the input data and indicate fair predictor variables (features) for the development of a DSS [16], [17]. According to their results, asking a more diverse group of workers (in terms of age, gender, race, and income) resulted in a closer alignment among group members with the overall majority than when a lower diversity group of crowdworkers participated in the task.

Others found that the demographic characteristics (i.e., age, gender, race, education etc.) of crowdworkers and their social beliefs can be propagated while collecting data for auditing an AI algorithm. For instance, in [18], sexist workers (as tested per a standard psychological measure) were less likely to report gender biases in image search results. Social beliefs of crowdworkers are also propagated through annotation tasks. Dong et al. [19] found that American and Chinese workers tag images in different ways and suggest that this is correlated to cultural differences. Nicholls et al. [20] showed that in face perception tasks, a crowdworker’s own age subconsciously biases their responses. Young workers were able to estimate better the age of young people and older workers the age

Fig. 1: Four images from the CFD (left to right: BF-232, BM-026, WF-243, WM-249)

of older people. Recent work [21] evaluates the behavior of crowdworkers as evaluators of the safety of conversations generated by humans talking to a generative AI-chat bot. Based on the results, crowdworkers’ demographics and the platform from which they have been recruited have an impact on the way they annotate a conversation as safe or harmful.

Drawing from the literature, there is sufficient evidence that increasing the diversity of a group of crowdworkers tasked to annotate data or audit an AI system, leads to more reliable, potentially less biased, outcomes. In this work, our goal is to investigate the importance of using a diverse group of crowdworkers for auditing algorithmic behaviors of an *intermediary* black-box process (i.e., of image-tagging cognitive services) of a DSS. Furthermore, we provide evidence that a potentially harmful algorithmic behavior in one context, may be perceived differently in a another domain or context.

III. METHODOLOGY

We propose to audit the output of a black-box AI algorithm exhibiting some sort of “behavior”, with respect to the input image to the black-box algorithm that generated it, under the general setting of the DSS’s goal. We consider two examples of the respective DSS: (i) a hiring DSS, the decisions of which may potentially impact one’s professional career, and (ii) a dating DSS, which can impact one’s personal life. We examine four images in this study, as shown in Figure 1. These are highly standardized, passport-style images, taken from the Chicago Face Database [22], and for which each depicted person’s gender and race is self-reported. While these are arguably not very natural photographs, they are generic, and could be found in a range of different contexts (e.g., as part of a university or job application, or even at a social network).

A. Crowdsourcing Task Design

a) Task instructions.: Crowdworkers are informed a priori of the task objective and goals and they make informed decisions as to whether or not they desire to continue with the crowdsourcing task. The description of the task provides a brief overview of the context of a computer vision algorithm and what will be the task. In this case, the crowdworkers received the following information: “*Computer vision algorithms, that automatically produce a set of tags (a.k.a., word(s) or phrases) for a provided image are used lately in real-world applications (i.e., hiring software, dating site software, etc.) Below you can see an example of the tags provided by a computer vision application for [that image]. Thus, the outcome of a real-world application can depend on the tags provided by the computer vision algorithm. You will be shown an image of a person and you will be asked to provide three*

tags that describe that person. For the same image, you will be asked to consider two different application scenarios. What are the: (a) three tags that are inappropriate to be provided by a computer vision algorithm for that specific scenario; (b) three tags that are appropriate to be provided by a computer vision algorithm for that specific scenario. Additionally, we will ask you to complete a brief demographics questionnaire.”

b) Task content.: After answering two control questions, crowdworkers are asked to provide three descriptions of the depicted person using a maximum of two words. Then, they are presented sequentially with two DSS scenarios and they are asked for each scenario to provide three inappropriate and three appropriate tags. Below we include the two DSS scenarios as presented to the crowdworkers:

c) Hiring scenario. (Computer vision application scenario - A hiring software): A multi-national company uses software to help human resource managers screen the thousands of resumes they receive on a monthly basis. The software uses computer vision algorithms to analyze the photos submitted by applicants (like in the general information example provided above), and to collect tags (i.e., word(s)) that provide additional insights into applicants’ characteristics. Tags, together with other information, are used by the human resource managers for deciding which candidate to call for an interview. A branch of this company in your region has decided to adopt these screening processes.

d) Dating scenario. (Computer vision application scenario - A dating software): A multi-national company develops software that supports online dating communities across the world. When someone applies to join a community, the software uses image tagging algorithms to collect tags (i.e., word(s)) that can provide additional insights into the applicants’ characteristics, which may then be used to make possible matches. The company is planning to open a new dating community in your region and will use the photo screening software in its matching algorithms.

B. Experimental Set-up and Pre-processing

Our study received ethical approval from the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee. We recruited crowdworkers through the Clickworker platform [23]. For each of the four images, we recruited 20 men and 20 women from Italy and the same number from Germany. We rewarded each crowdworker with 1 euro and allowed a crowdworker to participate in all four crowdsourcing tasks (i.e., report on all the images). After receiving all responses from the workers, spam responses were discarded (i.e., incorrect responses to a control question and/or gibberish text), and we translated non-English tags.

IV. EXPLORING THE CROWDWORKER BEHAVIOR

After cleaning the data we collected a total of 3.720 tags from both scenarios, of which 1.425 constitute unique tags. For the hiring scenario, we had 1.860 tags, of which 871 were unique, and for the dating scenario, we had 1.860 tags, of which 892 were unique. For the two scenarios, of the 1.425 unique tags, we had 338 common tags in the dating and hiring

Fig. 2: Relative frequency of tags used in each scenario, for all tags used at least 10 times.

scenario. In a quantitative manner, we saw that 198 inappropriate tags were used at least once in both the hiring and dating scenario and 165 were the common appropriate tags. Thus, across scenarios, there was slightly more convergence among the workers regarding the inappropriate as compared to the appropriate tags. Next, we establish a base for our observation, looking at the tags on both scenarios at a high level and understanding the extent to which our results can be considered reliable. Moving on, we introduce two approaches for analyzing tags. Finally, we view the responses based on the diversity of the crowd (i.e., gender and country of residence).

A. Reliability of Responses

Our task was open-ended. Thus, crowdworkers could suggest any word or set of words they see as appropriate and inappropriate for each scenario. Considering how frequently a tag appeared in each scenario from distinct workers provides additional information on the behavior of the crowdworkers. Thus, we considered all tags that had occurred at least 10 times in the dataset of each respective scenario, comparing their relative frequencies (see Figure 2). The relative frequencies of the most popular tags (i.e., occurring at least 10 times) were computed on the number of times a tag was mentioned in a certain scenario over all the tags received for that scenario. Note that, if a specific crowdworker reported the same tag, more than once for a specific image, we only counted that tag once. As expected, not all tags were used by workers in both scenarios. We notice that “young” is the most popular tag among the workers in both scenarios, while “serious” is much more popular in the hiring versus the dating scenario. Additionally, “nice”, “sexy”, “attractive” and “beautiful” are not in the most popular tags in the hiring, compared to the dating, scenario. However, “professional” and “reliable” are only in the most popular tags in the hiring scenario. Interestingly enough, identity tags like “man”, “woman”, “male”, “female”, “white”, “african”, “black”, “caucasian” are more popular or appear only in the hiring scenario. These high-level observations provide an indication that the crowdworkers were not only able to understand the assignment, provide reliable results, but also express a systematic behavior of matching tags to scenarios. Thus, we will explore under which conditions they express systematic behaviors and the characteristics of such behaviors.

B. Analysis based on semantic categories

To answer our research question, we need to “code” the open-ended responses. Thus, we analyze the tags under two perspectives: (1) general semantic categories meaningful to the application scenarios explored [redacted], (2) a Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) gold standard software for analyzing word use [24]. The following categories describe the tags received: age, identity, emotions, quality, status, external appearance, and inflammatory. The identity category includes tags like race, gender, nationality, etc., the quality category includes tags like “reliable”, and “determined”, and the status category includes tags describing a person’s life status like “married”, “single”, etc. We also consider the following categories from LIWC : drives, affect, social, lifestyle, culture, physical, motive, and perception categories. In our task, each “tag” reported by workers consists of 1 to 2 words. For each word that belongs to one of the LIWC categories, 0.5 is added to the LIWC frequency of that category (number of tags that are classified in that category). Thus, frequency 1 in LIWC might mean that either a 1-word tag, or both words of a 2-word tag, or a single word of two different 2-word tags has been classified in that category.

C. Diversity of the crowd: Gender

1) *General Semantic Categories Analysis*: Figure 3 explores the frequencies of the tags that workers reported as being appropriate and inappropriate for each scenario. To reduce noise, the analysis considers all tags that appeared at least five times. As a first observation, there are relatively few inappropriate tags reported in the dating scenario, which tells us that the crowdworkers are less in accordance (i.e., reporting the same tags) as compared to the other settings.

For the hiring scenario, regarding the issue of age, “young” and “young-woman” are considered mostly appropriate, while “old” is considered inappropriate. Introducing “old” as inappropriate was suggested by the male crowdworkers, while introducing “young-woman” as appropriate was suggested by females. On the other hand, for the dating scenario, “young”, “young-girl” and “adult” are considered appropriate, in that order according to frequency, while “old” is considered inappropriate. It appears that “young-girl” and “old” are suggested by male workers, while “adult” is suggested by females. We notice that the tag “old” has a negative connotation for male crowdworkers while females introduced “adult,” expressing a social norm in terms of who can participate in dating apps.

For the gender tags (e.g., “man”, “woman”, “male”, “female”), we notice that in both scenarios, there is a dichotomy among the crowdworkers as to whether the tag is appropriate or inappropriate in the hiring scenario, while in the dating scenario things are more clear; crowdworkers believe that such tags are appropriate to be reported in the dating scenario. In particular, it is interesting that the female crowdworkers often reported the tag “man” as inappropriate in the hiring scenario.

For tags that describe explicitly the origin of a person (e.g., “african”), we see that they are marked as inappropriate by females, just as “caucasian” is reported by males in the

Fig. 3: Frequencies of Appropriate (first row) and Inappropriate (second row) tags by worker gender. First column presents the hiring scenario and second column the dating scenario.

hiring scenario, while in the dating scenario, these tags are not reported as inappropriate. On the other hand, for tags that describe implicitly the origin of a person through the skin color (e.g., “white”, “black”), we can see that the majority considers them inappropriate in both scenarios. Note that only the tag “black” is considered appropriate by females in the hiring scenario and by both genders in the dating scenario.

Tags like, “serious”, “intelligent”, “professional”, “friendly”, “qualified”, “determined”, that express quality in a person, were frequently seen as appropriate in the hiring scenario, while tags like “unfriendly”, “stupid” and “lazy” were among the most inappropriate tags in the same scenario. Apparently female workers agree on more tags and provide a larger vocabulary of these types of tags. It is interesting to note that females suggest as appropriate the tag “friendly”, while males suggest as inappropriate the tag “unfriendly”. For the dating scenario, we can observe that both male and female crowdworkers suggest “friendly” as an appropriate tag, while males suggest “reliable” as appropriate and female crowdworkers suggest “intelligent” as appropriate. This last observation suggests that male and female crowdworkers express different social norms in the dating scenario.

Looking at tags that express status (e.g., “married”, “available”), they appear as inappropriate in the dating scenario, while “single” is appropriate. Apparently, these tags are introduced by females, who mention them more than five times in the open-ended task. Additionally, “single” is considered appropriate while “available” is inappropriate. This is a notable observation regarding the crowdworkers’ ability to express social norms, as “available” can have more than one meaning, while “single” is a more clear description of one’s status.

Crowdworkers reported a large variety of tags related to external appearance. Tags referring to the color or length of the

hair, or the color of the eyes, are considered appropriate in both scenarios. The only exception is of males finding “short-hair” inappropriate in the dating scenario. Additionally, the majority of external appearance tags are considered appropriate in the dating scenario. “Sexy” is introduced as inappropriate in the hiring scenario by males, while both genders consider it inappropriate in the dating scenario. Only males consider “fat” inappropriate in the dating scenario, while in the hiring scenario, both consider it inappropriate. Note that different vocabulary is used by the two genders for the appropriate dating tags (i.e., males use “beautiful”, females use “pretty”).

2) *LIWC Analysis*: Considering the tags reported at least five times (see Figure 3 for the list of tags), a LIWC analysis was also performed. Table I depicts the number of tags provided by female and male workers on the dating scenario, that map onto the LIWC categories. Inappropriate tags provided by both genders fall with similar frequency on the same categories. Moreover, tags provided by males have a higher frequency on physical appearance. Regarding the appropriate tags for the dating scenario, females provide a higher number of tags relevant to social identities than males, who focus on physical appearance. For the hiring scenario (Table I), females provide a variety of appropriate tags in different categories (i.e., Drives, Physical and Perception), in contrast to males, who mostly provide tags related to social referents. As to the inappropriate tags, female workers provide more tags with negative sentiment as compared to males.

D. Diversity of the Crowd: Country of Residence

1) *General Semantic Categories Analysis*: Figure 4 portrays the way Italian and German workers tag the images. For both scenarios, apart from the tag “young” given by both groups, and “young-girl” given by Italians, Germans agreed on

LIWC Categories	Dating Scenario				Hiring Scenario				Dating Scenario				Hiring Scenario			
	Approp.		Inapprop.		Approp.		Inapprop.		Approp.		Inapprop.		Approp.		Inapprop.	
	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	GER	ITA	GER	ITA	GER	ITA	GER	ITA
Drives - (Affiliation, Achieve)	1	1	1	0	2	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	2	1	1	-
Affect - (tonePos, emoPos)	5	7.5	1	1	4	1	-	1	4	4.5	2	-	3	1	-	-
Affect - toneNeg	-	-	1	1	-	-	4	1	-	-	2	3	-	-	4	4
Affect - swear	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
Social - (socbehav, socrefs)	6	3.5	1	-	5.5	4	3	2	5	2.5	-	1	4	3	5	2
Culture	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Allure	1	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.5	1	-	-	-	0.5	-	-
Lifestyle	-	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2	-	-
Physical (health, sexual)	-	3	1	3	1	-	1	3	2.5	2.5	2.5	1.5	0.5	1.5	1	1
Perception	2	4	3	2.5	2	-	3	3	3	5.5	2.5	3	2	1	2.5	3

TABLE I: Appropriate and Inappropriate Tags Frequencies for the Dating and Hiring Scenario by Female/Male and German/Italian crowdworkers

Fig. 4: Frequencies of Appropriate (first row) and Inappropriate (second row) tags by worker country. First column presents the hiring scenario and second column the dating scenario.

more tags regarding “middle-aged” as appropriate in the hiring scenario and “old” as inappropriate in the dating scenario.

Neither Italians nor Germans considered gender tags as inappropriate in the dating scenario. As for tags that describe a person’s origin, “african” was provided by Italian crowdworkers as inappropriate in the hiring scenario, while Germans provided “caucasian” as inappropriate. Although the tag “black” was considered inappropriate by both groups in the dating scenario, “white” was only treated as inappropriate by Germans. Some Italians considered “white” as appropriate in the dating scenario while some Germans considered “black” as appropriate in both scenarios.

Regarding tags that express the quality of a person, the majority of inappropriate tags were provided by Germans in both scenarios, while an almost equal amount of appropriate tags was provided in both scenarios. Notice that for appropriate tags in the dating scenario describing quality, German and Italian crowdworkers had no common tags.

Concerning tags expressing a person’s status, Italians suggested “worker” as appropriate in the hiring scenario, while

they consider “single” as appropriate and “married” and “available” as inappropriate in the dating scenario. Italians also suggested that emotions like “sad” should also be considered inappropriate in the hiring scenario. The above tag suggestions from Italian workers might expose some societal norms.

As to external appearance, Italians, in both scenarios but especially in the dating scenario, agreed on multiple tags both appropriate and inappropriate. Apart from characteristics referring to the hair and color of the eyes, they introduced “dirty” as inappropriate in both scenarios. Furthermore, in the appropriate tags for the dating scenario, Italians and Germans introduced different tags to describe a person as good-looking. Finally, in both scenarios, both types of crowdworkers agreed that tags like “ugly” and “fat” are inappropriate.

2) *LIWC Analysis*: As shown in Table I, for the dating scenario, Germans provide more diverse appropriate tags than Italians. They also provide appropriate tags related to categories Drives and Social, which capture affiliation and social behavior-related tags that were not provided by Italians. Italians, on the other hand, provide more visual tags (Perception).

Regarding the inappropriate tags, more Italians provide visual tags relevant to perception, compared to Germans. In addition, Italians provide tags classified in the categories Drives and Social which capture affiliation and social reference tags that were not provided by Germans. As shown in Table I, for the hiring scenario, Italians provide a higher number of appropriate tags related to physical appearance (Physical, Allure) while Germans focus more on tags related to motives and drives (Drive) and social-related tags. Regarding the inappropriate tags, Germans provide a higher number of social-related tags than Italians.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This work proposed crowdsourcing as a means to audit the behaviors of image analysis services. We aimed to discover the *social norms* that people expect the services to respect, when embedded into a DSS. We explored the potential of an open-ended task through which workers express tags that they consider appropriate and inappropriate under certain circumstances (i.e., the DSS application scenario). As discussed in Section IV-A, workers are able to distinguish preferred norms for each DSS scenario, which supports the feasibility of the approach. To explore whether diverse crowds express different social norms for the services, we pursued two distinct paths of analysis of the collected responses. In particular, we considered whether self-identified male and female crowdworkers, who reside in different countries with distinct cultural characteristics (Italy vs. Germany) suggest similar or differing appropriate and inappropriate tags.

Our analysis focused on the set of tags workers provided, which occurred at least five times (see Figures 3 and 4), to avoid noise and to identify common trends. Our results indicate that, in all semantic categories considered (i.e., age, identity, etc.) the tags provided by male and female crowdworkers displayed interesting differences, thus concluding that an equal weight on the opinion of both genders must be taken on this type of crowdsourcing task. This observation is supported by the LIWC analysis where quantitatively, we can see that male and female crowdworkers have a complementary effect on the tags they provide according to the LIWC categories.

Looking at the tags received from workers across country, we notice that workers of the same country agree on different tags under the external appearance semantic category, resulting in a more diverse vocabulary of tags to express appropriate and inappropriate tags for the two DSS scenarios. The LIWC analysis showed that for the same scenario and the appropriate/inappropriate tags, Italians and Germans provided tags on the same categories, but with different frequencies. Thus, in terms of harvesting the perceptions of both genders equally, we notice that this can provide a benefit in providing different types of tags, in terms of semantic content. On the other hand, harvesting the perceptions of crowdworkers in different regions, might provide a diversity on the tags provided under the same semantic category.

This work presents the initial results of a crowdsourced auditing approach for black-box image taggers typically em-

bedded into larger DSS. As such, we have chosen to show a limited number of images to the crowdworkers, but harvest multiple responses from them to answer our research question. In the future, we plan to run larger scale experiments, considering more images from CFD and reducing the number of judgements on each image.

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